

A Binomial Expansion equal to Multiple of 2 with Non-Negative Exponents

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: The binomial and combinatorial techniques are used in different ways to find the binomial theorems for using these applications in computing science and other academic and research areas. This paper presents a theorem on the multiple of two with positive exponents.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10

Keywords: binomial theorem, theoretical computer science, exponents, combinatorics

1. Introduction

Let us compare the traditional coefficient (traditional combination) and innovative coefficient or optimized combination [2-6].

Traditional coefficient: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N \cup \{0\}$ & $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Optimized combination: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\dots(r+n)}{n!}$, ($n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$).

Here, $V_r^{n-r} = nC_r = nC_{n-r}$ and $V_r^n = pC_r$, where $p = n + r$.

$$V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1 \text{ \& } V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1.$$

2. Binomial Theorem

The binomial theorem for multiple of 2 with non-exponents is given below:

Theorem: $\sum_{i=0}^n (i+1)V_i^{n-i} = (n+2)2^{n-1}$.

Proof: The binomial theorem is proved using the existing results [7], that is,

Result 1: $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n$ and Result 2: $\sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}$.

We can constitute the new binomial theorem by adding the existing results.

$$\sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1)V_i^{n-i} = (n+2)2^{n-1}.$$

Let us find the general term of new binomial theorem or binomial expansion using the sum of two general terms in the existing binomial series or binomial expansions [7].

$$r \times V_r^{n-r} + V_r^{n-r} = (r+1)V_r^{n-r}.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

$$\text{Corollary: } \sum_{i=0}^n (i-1)V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} - \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = (n-2)2^{n-1}$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, we discussed the binomial and combinatorial technique including optimized combination (innovative binomial coefficients) and also proved theorems with binomial expansion of coefficients that is equal to multiple of two with non-negative exponents. These binomial and combinatorial techniques will be of immediate interest to a broader readership of researchers in computational science and medicine [1].

References

- [1] Annamalai C (2010) “Application of Exponential Decay and Geometric Series in Effective Medicine”, *Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology*, Vol. 1(1), pp 51-54. <https://doi.org/10.4236/abb.2010.11008>.
- [2] Annamalai C (2020) “Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics”, hal-0286583. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9p4ek>.
- [3] Annamalai C (2020) “Novel Computing Technique in Combinatorics”, hal-02862222. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9re5>.
- [4] Annamalai C (2022) “Comparison between Optimized and Traditional Combinations of Combinatorics”, OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2qdyz>.
- [5] Annamalai C (2022) “Novel Binomial Series and its Summations”, Authorea Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.164933885.53684288/v2>.
- [6] Annamalai C (2022) “Annamalai’s Binomial Identity and Theorem”, SSRN. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [7] Annamalai C (2022) “Combinatorial Theorem for Multiple of Two with Exponents”, OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/awu6b>